

CORRECTIVE-PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISM FOR SPEECH DISORDERS IN CHILDREN WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS

F.K. Khaytova

Independent Researcher at Chirchik State Pedagogical University, Assistant at Samarkand State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *The given article presents the psycho-corrective and correctional-specific mechanisms of speech development in blind children, along with a comparative analysis of various scholars' views. It also highlights that overcoming speech disorders in blind children should be carried out through the integrated unity of pedagogical, psychological, and corrective approaches.*

Keywords: *correction, sensory, tactile, verbal, play activity, expressive, motor skills, perception, sensation.*

Introduction

In students with visual impairments, the formation of sensation, perception, and imagination is extremely complex. In this context, it is necessary to clarify the concept of sensation. A person perceives surrounding objects and phenomena through hearing, vision, smell, taste, and tactile sensations. In children with visual impairments, the function of vision is compensated by other sensory organs. A blind child primarily perceives surrounding objects and events through tactile sensations, especially by using their hands. These sensations help them form perceptions of objects.

The corrective basis of speech in blind children refers to a scientifically grounded system aimed at eliminating secondary deficiencies in speech development that arise due to impairment of the visual analyzer. Speech therapy correction is directed at developing all components of speech in blind children. This includes forming correct pronunciation, identifying and enriching vocabulary, improving grammatical structure, and developing coherent speech. In conducting corrective speech therapy work, it is essential to take into account the internal capabilities of blind children.

Children with visual impairments do not have a complete understanding of objects and phenomena in their environment. As a result, they often acquire many words and expressions mechanically, without understanding their meaning or being able to connect them with practical experience. Therefore, in corrective sessions, special attention is given not only to developing knowledge and skills but also to fostering positive emotional attitudes. This allows children to feel confident and comfortable. Special corrective sessions help improve the processes of education, upbringing, vocational guidance, preparation for work, and adaptation to independent life for children with visual impairments. The main goal is to prepare them to perceive educational material in general education classes and to engage in independent activities.

Purpose of the Study: To study and analyze the corrective-pedagogical aspects of speech deficiencies in blind children.

Objectives of the Study:

Corrective-pedagogical work carried out with children with visual impairments addresses the following tasks:

- Developing skills for the proper use of residual vision;
- Teaching how to obtain information about the surrounding world through all preserved analyzers;
- Teaching how to use the acquired polysensory information in subject-practical, cognitive, and communicative activities, as well as in spatial orientation.

Additionally, one of the most important tasks of corrective sessions is to develop socially adaptive behavior skills in children. This enables them to be independent and sufficiently active in daily life, social situations, and communication with peers and adults.

Relevance of the Topic: At present, in the fields of special pedagogy and speech therapy, the development of speech in blind and visually impaired children is an actual scientific and practical issue. The specific characteristics of speech in blind children necessitate the development of special corrective-pedagogical mechanisms, the improvement of their theoretical foundations, and the identification of effective methods and technologies. Speech therapy intervention is carried out through a complex of generally accepted methods practical, visual, and verbal approaches. To prevent the formation of purely verbal representations, verbal methods are used in combination with visual and practical methods. Since play activity develops more slowly in this category of children, speech therapy sessions are organized in a play-based format using game materials. Didactic and visual materials are selected with consideration of the children’s visual pathology.

Level of Study of the topic: Collaboration among speech therapists, typhlopedagogues, and medical professionals makes it possible to teach children to perceive information about the environment through preserved analyzers. As a result, their speech gains clearer content, becoming more vivid and enriched.

Pedagogical, Psychological, and Corrective Features of Eliminating Speech Disorders in Blind Children: A Comparative Analysis with International Research

Direction	National (Local) Approaches	International Research and Practice	Common and Distinguishing Features
Pedagogical Approach	Education in specialized schools and classes relying on oral speech; sensory compensation (hearing, tactile sense)	Inclusive education prioritized in US and European studies; multisensory approach (auditory, tactile, kinesthetic) widely used	Common feature – sensory compensation; Difference – international experience emphasizes inclusion and broader use of technologies
Educational Tools	Braille, audio materials, object-based lessons	Braille + digital assistive technologies (screen readers, audiobooks, interactive programs)	International experience shows wider technological opportunities

Vocabulary Development	Teaching words by linking them with objects and actions	Development through experiential language learning and real-life situations (research by Hatwell, Warren)	Methodological foundations are similar; contextual richness is stronger in international experience
Psychological Approach	Emotional support, creating positive motivation	International studies apply self-efficacy and social-emotional learning (SEL) concepts	Goal is the same; theoretical foundation is deeper in international experience
Communication Skills Development 	Conversations, role-playing, individual lessons	Social stories and group training in the USA and Scandinavian countries	Social integration is stronger in the international approach
Speech Correction and Therapy	Individual speech therapy sessions, correcting sound pronunciation	Early intervention and multidisciplinary teams (speech therapist, psychologist, teacher for visually impaired) in international practice	Early diagnosis is prioritized in international experience
 Articulation Exercises	Tactile-articulation exercises, work on breathing and voice	Sensorimotor approach applied based on scientific evidence (research by ASHA)	Methods are similar; scientific standardization is stronger in international experience
Phonemic Hearing	Exercises based on auditory analysis	Development of phonological awareness considered a key factor in international studies	Content is similar; terminological differences exist
Connected Speech	Story creation, retelling	Narrative competence concept widely applied in international approach	Approaches are similar in content
Assessment of Effectiveness 	Observation and pedagogical diagnostics	Standardized tests and monitoring systems in international practice	Assessment mechanisms are more defined in international experience

Analysis Results:

The analysis shows that although national and international approaches to eliminating speech disorders in blind children are methodologically similar, international practice demonstrates a higher level of implementation of inclusive education, early intervention, multidisciplinary approaches, and the use of assistive technologies. Adapting these practices to the national education system can ensure more effective speech development in blind children.

Methods:

1. Identification and analysis of literature related to the topic;
2. Study of the psychological aspects of the topic;
3. Observation;
4. Comparative analysis.

Speech development in children with visual impairments has specific characteristics, directly affecting their cognitive activity, perception of the environment, and social adaptation processes. Speech disorders in blind children are often explained by limited sensory experience, insufficient formation of visual representations, and the passivity of speech activity. Therefore, addressing speech disorders in this category of children should be carried out through the integrated unity of pedagogical, psychological, and corrective approaches.

From a pedagogical perspective, the educational process for blind children requires a specially organized environment. In this process, the deficiency of the visual analyzer is compensated by other analyzers—hearing, tactile, and kinesthetic sensations. In teaching, explanations based on oral speech, object-based activities, tactile perception of objects, and linking words and concepts with real actions are of great importance. Pedagogical work is aimed at the systematic development of all components of speech—vocabulary, grammatical structure, sound pronunciation, and coherent speech.

Levels of Speech Development in Children with Visual Impairments
(According to L.S. Volkova)

First Level: Expressive speech does not perform a communicative function and is extremely limited. There are significant difficulties in linking words with object images and generalized concepts. Coherent speech consists of isolated words. Echolalia is observed. The processes of phonemic analysis and synthesis are not fully developed.

Second Level: Expressive speech is characterized by limited vocabulary. The connection between words and object images, as well as the understanding of generalized concepts, is at a low level. Coherent speech is agrammatical and consists of enumerations and one- or two-word sentences. There are numerous sound pronunciation disorders. The ability to distinguish sounds by hearing and pronunciation is insufficiently developed. Phonemic analysis and synthesis are poorly developed.

Third Level: Active vocabulary is limited. Errors occur in matching words with object images, in the use of generalized concepts, grammatical categories, sentence construction, and in producing extended narratives. Sound pronunciation is impaired. The differentiation of sounds by hearing and pronunciation, as well as phonemic representations, are insufficiently developed.

Fourth Level: Isolated (single) sound pronunciation disorders are observed.

Psychological Aspects: From a psychological perspective, speech disorders in blind children are often closely related to emotional state and personal development. Visual impairment can lead to lack of self-confidence, withdrawal from communication, and decreased speech activity. Therefore, psychological support is an essential condition for speech development. By fostering positive motivation, strengthening the need for communication, and ensuring emotional stability, it is possible to activate speech activity. Activities based on play, conversation, and social situations are considered effective psychological tools.

Classification of Children with Visual Impairments:

1. Children who are congenitally blind or who became blind or visually impaired before the age of three due to various negative factors;

2. Children who acquired visual impairment after the age of three.

The main criterion for such classification is the extent of life experience and visual representations the child accumulated during the period of normal vision (if such a period existed).

Difficulties in Developing Communication Skills: Visual impairment limits social interactions and hinders the development of communication experience with peers and adults. Children may have difficulty recognizing interlocutors and understanding their emotions through facial expressions. They also struggle to adequately express their own emotions. The use of nonverbal means of communication facial expressions, gestures, and intonation—is often weak. As a result, speech becomes less expressive and requires special corrective work. These difficulties are especially pronounced in children with total or severe visual impairment.

Corrective Speech Therapy Work: Corrective-logopedic work is planned individually depending on the type and severity of speech disorders in blind children. The corrective process includes correcting sound pronunciation, developing phonemic hearing, forming lexical-grammatical structures, and developing coherent speech. Special attention is given to tactile-articulatory exercises, tasks based on auditory analysis, and work on speech breathing and voice. The effectiveness of corrective work increases when it is carried out in harmony with pedagogical and psychological approaches.

Continuity of Corrective Sessions: The continuity of corrective sessions is an important factor in working with visually impaired children within an educational cluster environment. This means that the educational process should be continuous and uninterrupted, as only in this way can children gradually acquire new knowledge and skills. Corrective sessions should be individualized and adapted to each child's needs and level of development. Therefore, it is important first to diagnose each child's developmental level and determine the necessary knowledge and skills.

In addition, the use of various teaching methods and technologies that help visually impaired children better understand educational material is of great importance. For example, audio and video materials, tactile cards, computer programs, and special technologies increase the effectiveness of the learning process. Cooperation with speech therapists, psychologists, and other specialists within the educational cluster also plays a key role in ensuring continuity of education. Such an approach improves the development of visually impaired children and enables their full participation in the educational process.

Children with visual impairments face certain difficulties in the learning process. The absence or limitation of visual perception and communication challenges complicate their learning. Therefore, adhering to the principle of continuity in corrective sessions is especially important. When developing educational programs, it is necessary to take into account children's existing knowledge, skills, and previous learning experiences.

- Developing skills for the effective use of residual vision;
- Teaching how to obtain information about the surrounding world through all preserved analyzers;
- Teaching how to use the acquired polysensory information in subject-practical, cognitive, and communicative activities, as well as in spatial orientation.

In addition, one of the most important tasks of corrective sessions is to develop socially adaptive behavior skills in children. This enables them to be independent and sufficiently active in daily life, social situations, and communication with peers and adults.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the process of eliminating speech disorders in blind children requires a comprehensive approach. The interconnection and systematic organization of pedagogical, psychological, and corrective work serve as key factors in ensuring children's speech development, as well as their social adaptation and personal growth.

At present, many teachers widely use classical individual lessons and small group sessions in their practice, as they provide an effective individualized and differentiated approach. This is very important in corrective-pedagogical work; however, in addition to these forms, significant attention is also given to integrated lessons. Today, integration is considered one of the effective ways to improve the quality of education, modernize it, and support the development of the child's personality, as well as preserve and strengthen their health. Integrated sessions focus on overall development rather than isolated processes. They help develop communication skills, motor activity, cognitive engagement, speech, spatial orientation, fine and gross motor skills, imagination, memory, and attention.

In recent years, approaches based on modern information and communication technologies have also been widely introduced in the development of speech in blind children. Audio materials, voice-based programs, electronic resources based on Braille, and special speech-development applications significantly increase the effectiveness of the corrective process.

This approach supports the development of independent work, listening comprehension, and speech activity in children, and serves as a complementary tool to traditional methods. Overall, current approaches to correcting speech deficiencies in blind children are comprehensive, systematic, and personality-oriented in nature. These approaches are based on the child's sensory capabilities, activity, and individual characteristics, and they ensure the effectiveness of the corrective-pedagogical process.

REFERENCES

1. Khalikov. *Methodological Guide for Forming Subject Concepts and Developing Visual Perception in Grade 1*. Tashkent: "Evrika" Publishing House LLC, 2024, p. 5.
2. F.U. Kodirova, Z.X. Khusnuddinova. *The Necessity of a Cluster Environment in Organizing Corrective-Pedagogical Work with Blind Children*. Proceedings of the Republican Scientific-Practical Conference, Andijan, April 9–10, 2025.
3. E.V. Orlova. *Features of Speech Development in Children with Visual Impairments*. Yekaterinburg, p. 39.
4. J. Toychiev. *Proceedings of the Young Scientists Scientific-Practical Conference*. Available at: in-academy.uz/index.php/yo
5. Qodirova, F. (2025). *The Necessity of a Cluster Environment in Organizing Corrective-Pedagogical Work with Blind Children*. Universal International Scientific Journal, 2(4.1). 352–353. Retrieved from https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/universaljurnal/article/view/86785file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/mak_hay-z_xus-6-23.pd